

Physiological and Perceptual Responses to Objects Presented in Visual and Tactile Modalities

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Abstract. We use our senses to interact with objects in our environment, where touch and haptics are pivotal. When the skin of our hands is in contact with an external object, tactile information is obtained, including discriminative (e.g. roughness, stickiness) and affective/emotional (e.g. pleasure, arousal) elements. We can also appreciate these characteristics via other senses, such as visually seeing the object. We aim to study the physiological responses associated with the touch of objects, particularly unpleasant objects, which we will compare with pleasant and neutral objects. We will use a set of predefined objects that have been characterized on these properties. Unpleasant touch, which has been little studied, does not evoke pain, but provokes a response that is emotionally negative and often highly pertinent, in contrast to neutral or positive emotional (e.g. pleasant affective touch) interactions. We will study bodily physiological responses from simply seeing, or touching, or using both senses, to assess objects, linking this with tactile perception. Our results should show differences between modalities and affective objects, where we predict seeing greater responses in the tactile and negative affective conditions.

Keywords: Affective Touch, Autonomic Nervous System, Body Physiological Responses

1 Introduction

When we touch objects, receptors in the skin and deeper tissue produce neuronal signals that provoke psychological responses (e.g. perception of pleasure) and physiological responses (e.g. increased sweating). The positive affective perception of touch has been extensively investigated through psychophysical studies, most often in relation to the emotional processing of a gentle, pleasant caress and measured through perceptual scales [1–3][1], [2]. Other studies have used neuroimaging to investigate central responses to gentle touch [4, 5] and a few have looked at bodily physiological responses [6, 7]. Concerning the human body’s physiological response to touch, it is possible to non-invasively measure different reactions, such as skin electrodermal activity (sweating rate), heart rate and its variability, respiration rate, facial electromyography, and pupil diameter. A further, invasive physiological approach can also be applied, namely

sympathetic microneurography [8], to explore directly the response of the autonomic nervous system to affective stimuli in humans, which is responsible for our body's homeostatic balance. This system is involved not only in controlling involuntary bodily functions, but also in cognitive and emotional states. In our planned experiments in healthy humans, we will present objects that have been characterized as pleasant, unpleasant, or neutral, either visually, through touch, or both. We aim to measure heart rate, respiration, electrodermal responses, and pupil dilation in a first set of experiments, then explore the sympathetic nervous system response via microneurography. We will also link this with perceptual measures and questionnaires about touch. We expect higher sympathetic nervous system responses to pleasant and unpleasant stimuli, compared to neutral stimuli, and higher parasympathetic nervous system responses (e.g. heart rate variability) to pleasant stimuli, compared to unpleasant and neutral ones. Moreover, we expect these responses to be higher for high pleasantness ratings compared to lower ratings in both modality (visual/tactile), but we expect that real touch, thus physical interactions, may lead to stronger effects than vision alone.

2 Method

To better understand the set of physiological responses to objects evaluated as pleasant (e.g. cosmetic brush), neutral (e.g. nylon rope), or unpleasant (e.g. sandpaper), during our experiments we will use visual images and we will ask participants to handle real objects (Fig. 1). Before the start of the experiment, the participant will complete questionnaires to inform us about the pleasantness perception of objects often experienced in everyday life (linked with the collaborative project “UNTOUCH” from which the objects were chosen), the general state of a person under specific situations (STAI-Y1ⁱ), and information about attitudes and experiences of touch (TEAQⁱⁱ). After, the participant is setup for the main experiment. A baseline of 5 minutes duration of autonomic physiological activity at rest is recorded. During this phase the electrodermal signal, heart rate, respiration, and pupillary dilation are recorded. Next, three tasks are carried out during the physiological recordings. In the first task, nine stimuli from each emotional category are presented visually, in turn. In the second task, four real objects per category are presented in turn, via a tactile haptic interaction using the hands, where they are instructed to explore them. In the third task, each of the same tactile stimuli are presented in visual and haptic modalities simultaneously. After each stimulus, the participant rates the pleasantness of the object using a visual analog scale.

Fig. 1. Left: example of an unpleasant tactile stimulus (sandpaper). Right: setup of a participant.

3. Expected Results

Our results should provide numerous insights into how the body reacts physiologically to affective stimuli presented in two major ways relevant to humans. Bodily responses differ over their timecourses, but we hope to gain markers of affect, potentially different for the different tactile and visual modalities, and for positive and negative stimuli. These effects could be further multiplied with combined vision and touch. The first series of experiments should allow us to conclude about bodily reactions through non-invasive measures, but we hope to use microneurography to directly examine the responses of the sympathetic nervous system, as well as seeing how this relates to the non-invasive measures. Our goal is to find physiological markers of affective haptic interactions, to understand these fundamental processes and apply them. We then aim to relate how participants specifically respond to such emotional stimuli, with regard to how they answer the questionnaires, to show links between sensory input and cognitive factors.

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ⁱSTAI-Y1 <https://institutneurosport.com/notice-stai.html>

ⁱⁱTEAQ short version <https://osf.io/qg5he>